

A Survey of Information Literacy Search Skills on the Utilisation of E-Resources in Federal University Otuoke Library, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of information literacy skills on the utilisation of electronic information resources in the University Library at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The research employed a descriptive survey design. Three research questions and a null hypothesis guided the study. The population comprised 2500 final-year undergraduates across the five faculties of Federal University Otuoke. Purposive sampling was used, selecting 250 undergraduates- representing ten per cent of the population- as respondents. Data were collected via a structured questionnaire titled: 'Information Literacy Skills and the Utilisation of Electronic Information Resources in the University Library Questionnaire (ILSUEIRULQ)' on a 4-point scale. The Spearman rank-order correlation method was used to assess the instrument's reliability. The researcher administered 250 copies of the questionnaire, and 234 were returned. Chi-square(x²) was employed to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings indicated no significant relationship between the information literacy skills of undergraduates at Federal University Otuoke and the utilisation of electronic information resources in the library. The study revealed a high level of information literacy, as well as the ability to assess the authoritativeness, correctness, and reliability of sources when accessing electronic resources. It also found that very few undergraduates utilise e-resources in the university library. Consequently, it is recommended that, to enhance undergraduates' understanding of information literacy skills, the University Library, in collaboration with the Institute for Foundation Studies (IFS), should focus on teaching information literacy through workshops and during lectures, supported by.

Keywords: Information literacy, E-Resources, search skills, information, literacy

Introduction

The concept of information literacy extends beyond knowing how to find books in the library. Many aspects of information literacy are important parts of education. The amount of information available to undergraduates through library resources, electronic databases, and the internet is overwhelming these days. This situation presents a significant challenge for undergraduates in how to communicate information wisely, efficiently, and effectively through practical experiences. This challenge has grown beyond the university walls. To address these challenges, the importance of information literacy skills cannot be overstated, as they help students and professionals to narrow or broaden a topic to learn,

synthesise information to create new knowledge, and reinforce and build on information management skills.

Information has become an essential commodity, and the nation needs to educate people for productive use of information, from pre-school through post-secondary education. Igbnlola, Akubua, and Adenigbo (2019) described information literacy as a 21st-century issue that is important and strategic in all areas of society. Explaining the term, the Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL) (2015) defined information literacy as a set of integrated abilities that include the reflective discovery of information, understanding how information is produced and valued, and using information to create new knowledge and ethically participate in communities of learning. In their opinion, Ekong and Ekong (2018) regard information literacy as the ability of individuals to locate and critically evaluate information. It also involves the capacity to use information effectively in decision-making and knowledge creation. According to the researchers, users of information resources must possess information literacy skills to effectively harness them. They must also acquire the knowledge and techniques for exploring information for problem-solving and decision-making in our ever-changing technological world, which has led to the development of information literacy skills that enable users to obtain the necessary information.

Oakleaf and Owen (2010) emphasise that the digitisation of information, also known as electronic information, has introduced a new concept across all fields of life. This digitisation marked the start of the information age, with nearly every new print resource now available electronically (Irenoa & Sawyerr-george, 2022). Electronic information can be defined as a resource accessible via a computer or other electronic device that provides a collection of data, typically in the form of full-text databases, electronic journals, image collections, and other multimedia products. These can be delivered via CD-ROM, tape, the internet, etc., and are considered more useful and durable due to their inherent capabilities for manipulation, searching, access, storage, and maintenance. Electronic information resources require computer access or another electronic device to deliver data, such as electronic journals, image collections, and multimedia products. Thanuskodi (2012) states that electronic resources are digital representations of information available in various formats, such as e-books, digital libraries, online journals, and magazines. According to Bankole, Ajibayo, and Otuola (2015), electronic information resources include resources in electronic formats such as the internet, CD-ROMs, databases, and e-books. Therefore, information literacy skills and the utilisation of electronic information resources in university libraries by undergraduates involve the ability to gather facts and to identify, locate, evaluate, and effectively use electronic information to meet the educational needs of undergraduates in Nigeria, especially at the Federal University, Otuoke.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid growth of information resources in electronic format has posed challenges for both users and librarians in retrieving relevant information or documents. Research indicates that one difficulty faced by students or undergraduates in accessing and using information effectively is their lack of information literacy skills. Electronic information resources have given 21st-century students privileges that were not available to previous generations. However, a large number of undergraduates still leave university without the necessary skills to manage an information-based society. It is observed, among other issues, that the effective use of electronic resources in academic institutions is hindered by various factors such as a lack of retrieval skills, poor information literacy, and evaluation skills. Furthermore, users of electronic resources often encounter more information than they can effectively handle. To address this problem of

information overload, skills are required to locate and verify the quality of information obtained from electronic sources. Therefore, it is important to investigate whether these information literacy skills influence the utilisation of electronic resources by undergraduates of Federal University, Otuoke.

Research Questions

- 1: What are the search skills/techniques and retrieval tools used by undergraduates of Federal University Otuoke in accessing e-resources
- 2: what is the level of computer proficiency of undergraduates of Federal University Otuoke in the use of e-resources
- 3: what is the e-resource used by undergraduates of Federal University, Otuoke

Hypothesis

H₁ There is no significant relationship between the information literacy skills of the undergraduates of Federal University, Otuoke and the use of electronic information resources.

Review of Related Literature

Information literacy skills of undergraduates

The information literacy skills of undergraduates enable them to master content and expand their research, becoming more self- directed and taking greater control over their own learning. Ashikuzzama (2019) stated that the fundamental goal of information literacy skills (ILS) is to cultivate critical users of information. IL is regarded as a powerful tool for lifelong learning; it is universal across all disciplines, learning environments, and educational levels. The primary mission of educational institutions should be to develop lifelong skills and support continuous growth throughout students' careers. A lack of information literacy skills can lead to inadequate, ineffective, and inefficient use of library resources. Issa, Amusan, and Daina (2009) argued that undergraduates need a certain level of information literacy skills to make informed decisions about academic matters and various aspects of their daily lives. Based on scholarly observations, it is clear that when using electronic resources, undergraduates often lack the skills to locate and evaluate information, which acts as a barrier to their effective utilisation of electronic resources. The ability to find, retrieve, and synthesise information efficiently is a transferable skill vital for future life and for empowering positive and successful use of electronic information resources in university libraries. Unfortunately, students often do not appreciate the skills required to search these sources, mainly because they dislike reading on screens, which affects their eyesight, or because of poor electricity supply. Toyo (2017), in his research on Undergraduates' Information Literacy Skills and the Use of Electronic Resources in Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria, found that 97.97.6% of respondents agreed they could recognise the information needed; 117 (96.7%) possessed skills to search for information online; 110 (90.9%) had skills to utilise information sources; 104 (86%) knew how to incorporate information into their knowledge base; 102 (71.1%) possessed skills in saving and editing e-resources; and 99 (81.8%) had the ability to evaluate information appropriately.

Electronic Information Resources Available in University Libraries

Electronic information resources are those contained within electronic devices or digital data. In today's information age, most libraries and information centres house various electronic information.

Elis and Oldman (2005) identified the electronic information resources most libraries house as the internet, CD-ROMs, databases, e-books, e-journals, online public access catalogues, and other computer-based electronic networks. In his 2017 research on the electronic resources available and commonly used by undergraduates of Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria, Toyo (2017) revealed that 121 (100%) agreed that they utilise websites and the internet. Other electronic resources used by the undergraduate LIS students include e-Discussions 120 (99.2%), e-News 119 (98.3%), online magazines 114 (94.2%), e-journals 111 (91.7%), CD-ROM 100 (82.6%), and e-books 96 (79.3%). However, online databases and e-data archives recorded low usability, with only 68 (56.2%) and 29 (24%) of respondents respectively affirming their use. This analysis, therefore, indicates that the majority of undergraduate LIS students utilise various electronic resources.

Benefits of the use of E-resources by undergraduates

E-resources are invaluable research tools that complement the print-based resources in a traditional library setting, and their advantages cannot be overemphasised. Dilek-Kayaoglu (2008), in research on the use of electronic journals by faculty and students at Istanbul University, also found that the majority of respondents supported the transition from print to electronic resources due to the numerous opportunities they offer. Studies have also been conducted on the use of electronic resources by teachers, students, and research scholars of universities and research organisations. Seventy-eight per cent (78%) of the respondents feel that the use of the OPAC, e-books, e-mail, e-reference sources, e-journals, etc., has created a high level of dependence in their research work, and they require current article alert services and electronic document supply services. Toyo (2017), in a study, reveals that the benefits derived by undergraduate LIS students from the use of electronic resources include instructional delivery to support teaching and research activities, ease of use, access to a wider range of information, and aid in access and retrieval of information, as indicated by 121 (100%) of the respondents. Other benefits include improvements in general communication, as reported by 120 (99.2%), enhanced overall academic performance, as reported by 119 (98.3%), and a high degree of dependence on research work, as reported by 88 (72.7%). Thus, this analysis concludes that undergraduate LIS students gain significant benefits from using electronic resources.

Search Techniques and ICT Proficiency by Undergraduate Students

The library subscribes to many online resources, including bibliographic databases and full-text e-journals, similar to websites. Xie and Joo (2010) conducted research on factors affecting the selection of search tactics: Tasks, knowledge, process, and systems. This study investigated whether and how different factors related to tasks, user-perceived knowledge, search process, and systems influence users' choice of search tactics. Thirty-one participants, representing the public, were recruited for this study. In the study, a total of 3756 tactics were observed across 60 search tasks performed by these participants. Major tactics are frequently used, such as AccF, AccB, EvalR, EvalI, and Use, whereas minor tactics are less frequently used, such as Lead, Mod, Org, and Rec (Xie & Joo, 2010).

Xie and Joo (2010) highlighted the following as search strategies:

- Boolean Operators
- Phrase searching

- Proximity search
- Fuzzy Search • Stemming
- Truncation searches
- Wildcard searches

Umeji et al. (2013) investigated information and ICT literacy levels and skills among librarians at Madonna University Library, Okija. The main purpose of this study was to determine the ICT literacy levels and skills among professional librarians in Madonna University Library, Okija. The specific objectives included examining in-depth concepts of information and digital literacy/skills in the 21st century, identifying the types of digital literacy and skills in the electronic age, and uncovering the skills and knowledge staff possess in using digital libraries. The study revealed that 5 (45.45%) of the librarians had a poor level of ICT literacy, 5 (45.45%) showed lukewarm attitudes towards the profession, and 1 (18.1%) lacked knowledge. This indicated that the librarians at Madonna University are very deficient in information and ICT literacy and skills. These deficiencies have affected the quality of services provided to patrons over the years. Furthermore, most of the challenges faced by Madonna University librarians were that ICT facilities were available but not used for service delivery. The reason for this is their lack of ICT literacy and 21st-century skills. Anafo, P. and Filson, C. (2014) conducted a survey on promoting information literacy among undergraduate students at Ashesi University College. At the time of the research, the university had approximately five hundred and fifty (550) students. A sample of two hundred students, representing 200. 36.4% was considered sufficient to produce reliable results. This exceeds the 10% required to represent the total population in a survey. The findings showed that, in terms of concept identification, an average of 60% of the student respondents had difficulty identifying significant words, even when provided with a list of possible answers. The situation at Ashesi University College is comparable to that at Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, both in Ghana.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive research design. The population included students from the faculties of Education, Science, Humanities and Social Sciences, Engineering, and Management Science, totalling approximately two thousand five hundred (2500) undergraduates. The sample size for this study was two hundred and fifty (250) undergraduates, representing ten per cent (10%) of the population of 400-level undergraduates across the five faculties of the university (2500). The 400-level students were purposively selected because, as final-year students, they are expected to have acquired information literacy skills. A purposive sampling technique was employed, and 250 undergraduates, constituting 10 per cent of the total population, served as respondents. A structured questionnaire titled "Information Literacy Skills and the Utilisation of Electronic Information Resources in the University Library Questionnaire (ILSUEIRULQ)" was used to collect data on a 4-point scale. The Spearman rank-order correlation method was used to assess the instrument's reliability. The researcher distributed 250 copies of the questionnaire to respondents, and 234 were returned. Chi-square (χ^2) was used to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 significance level.

Findings

Distribution of population

SN	Faculty	No of 400-level students	10%
1	Education	680	68
2	Engineering	312	31.2

3	Humanity and Social Science	550	55
4	Science	458	45.8
5	Management science	500	50
Total		2500	250

Table 1: Distribution of Population of the Study

This information was obtained from the university's admissions office.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between the information literacy skills of the undergraduates of Federal University, Otuoke, and their use of electronic information resources. In testing the hypothesis, the information skills of the undergraduates of Federal University, Otuoke, were assessed based on their agreement regarding the use of electronic information resources. To evaluate the hypothesis, the Chi-Square (X^2) test of significance was employed. The test was conducted at a 0.05 level of significance. The results are presented in table 2 below.

Information Literacy Skills	Electronic Resources	Information	Total
	Positive	Negative	
Positive	47	107	154
Negative	19	61	80
Total	66	168	234

Table 2 Analysis of the relationship between the information literacy skills and e-resources

X^2 calculated = 1.1915
 X^2 critical = 3.841
 Degree of freedom = 1
 P – value = 0.275
 Level of significance = 0.05

Decision

The results presented in Table 4.8 indicate that the P-value of 0.275 exceeds the level of significance. Similarly, the calculated Chi-square value of 1.1915 is less than the critical value of 3.841. The null hypothesis tested is therefore accepted, implying that there is no significant relationship between the information literacy skills of undergraduates at Federal University, Otuoke, and the use of electronic information resources in the university library.

Research Question 2

What are the Search Techniques and Retrieval tools used by undergraduates of Federal University Otuoke

The search techniques and retrieval tools were measured using eight (8) items in the questionnaire. Table 3 shows respondents' responses regarding search skills and retrieval tools.

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Remark
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1	I use Boolean... I use Boolean operators to narrow down my research topics	100	75	37	22	Positive
2	I visit search engines (e.g., Yahoo, Google, Ask.com, Alta Vista. Etc.) for my research queries.	172	62	0	0	Positive
3	I do phrase searching to retrieve information e.g. Information retrieval; Global warming	127	82	19	6	Positive
4	I source information from university libraries database	130	61	32	11	Positive
5	I do key word searching e.g. information technology and combine two terms to retrieve information.	143	84	7	0	Positive
6	Use of truncation search techniques to retrieve information.	112	63	59	0	Positive
7	I use the electronic catalogue (OPAC) for sourcing information in the library,	151	30	31	22	Positive
8	I download files from online databases	205	10	13	16	Positive

Table 3

One hundred and seventy-five (175) respondents, representing 74.8%, agreed that they used Boolean operators to narrow down their research topics. All respondents confirmed that they used search engines such as Yahoo and Google for their research queries. Two hundred and nine (209), or 89.3%, agreed that they phrased their search terms to retrieve information. One hundred and ninety-one (191), or 81.6%, agreed that they sourced information from the university library database. Two hundred and twenty-seven (227), or 97%, agreed that they performed keyword searches. One hundred and seventy-five (175), or 74.8%, used truncation search techniques to retrieve information. One hundred and eighty-one (181), or 77.4%, agreed that they used the electronic catalogue for sourcing information in the library. Two hundred and fifteen (215), or 91.9%, downloaded files from online databases.

The results in Table 3 indicate that the above-listed items are the search skills, techniques, and retrieval tools used by undergraduates of the Federal University Otuoke in accessing e-resources.

Research Question 3

What is the level of computer proficiency of undergraduates of Federal University Otuoke in the use of e-resources?

The level of computer proficiency was measured with seven (7) items in the questionnaire. Table 4 shows how the responses collected were presented in the table below:

S/N	Statement	VHL	HL	LL	VLL	Remark
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1	I am confident in using the computer mouse	164	15	5	50	Positive
2	I am confident in using a computer keyboard efficiently	152	33	49	0	Positive
3	I am confident in adding and deleting information from a data file	168	16	50	0	Positive
4	I am confident in making selections from the screen menu	160	34	40	0	Positive
5	I understand the data processing inputs and output processing	156	26	2	50	Positive
6	I understand the use of different operating systems e.g., Windows	101	26	107	0	Positive
7	I am confident in entering, copying and saving individual files	144	40	50	0	Positive

Table 4 shows computer proficiency levels

One hundred and seventy-nine (179) respondents, 76.5%, expressed high confidence in using a computer mouse. One hundred and eighty-five (185) respondents, 79%, expressed high confidence in using computer keyboards. One hundred and eighty-four (184), 78.6% of the respondents agreed to a high level of confidence in adding and deleting information from a data file. One hundred and ninety-four (194) respondents, 82.9%, expressed high confidence in selecting items from computer screen menus. One hundred and eighty-two (182), 77.7% of the respondents indicated that they understood data processing (input and output processing). One hundred and twenty-seven (127), 54.3% of respondents reported a high level of understanding and utilisation of different operating systems. One hundred and eighty-four (184), 78.6% of the respondents displayed high dexterity in entering, copying, and saving individual files.

The results in Table 4 show that the above responses indicate a high level of computer proficiency among undergraduates at the Federal University Otuoke in the use of e-resources.

Research Question 4

What are the electronic resources used by undergraduates of the Federal University Otuoke?

The electronic information resources utilised by undergraduates at the Federal University Otuoke, were assessed using five (5) items in the research questionnaire. Table 5 presents participants' responses regarding their use of electronic resources.

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Remark
1	We use OPAC	23	54	56	101	Negative
2	Online Databases are available and accessible	41	34	63	96	Negative
3	E- journal articles are in supply	11	67	49	109	Negative
4	We have access to an E-book	17	56	50	111	Negative

5	CD-ROMs are made available for use	21	53	45	115	Negative
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Table 5 shows responses on the use of e-resources

157 (67.1%) respondents disagreed that OPAC was an e-resource used in the university. 159 (67.9%) respondents disagreed that online databases were used in the university. 158 (67.5%) respondents disagreed that e-journal articles were utilised within the university. 161 (68.8%) respondents disagreed with the use of e-books in the university. 160 (68.4%) respondents identified the absence of CD-ROMs as an e-resource in the university. From the results in Table 5, most undergraduates disagreed with the availability of e-resources in the university library.

Conclusion

Given the high prevalence of propaganda, misinformation, and fake news across various online channels, the importance of information literacy in the teaching and learning environment cannot be overstated. Results indicate that undergraduate students at the Federal University, Otuoke, were highly aware of the subscribed e-resources, from which they gained multiple benefits and used frequently for academic purposes. Therefore, the level of e-resource usage reflected both the benefits obtained and the students' awareness. Despite adequate computer skills, many students lacked the necessary skills to access e-resources due to insufficient training. Lack of access and limited institutional support were identified as primary barriers. Moreover, although efforts have been made to provide various e-resources and support facilities, off-campus access remains limited. This issue is worsened by frequent power outages at off-campus locations such as homes and internet cafes, slow internet speeds, and other problems. Nonetheless, students continued to utilise e-resources because of the benefits they provide to their studies.

Recommendation

The study recommends the following based on the findings and conclusions.

- i. The study recommends that for undergraduates to have a better understanding of information literacy, the university library, in conjunction with the Institute for Foundation Studies (IFS), must focus on teaching the undergraduates to be information literate through workshops and during lecture periods backed with practical experiences.
- ii. The study also recommends that more publicity be carried out on the Programmes, resources and activities of the university library through fliers, posters and social media channels.

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